

Cultural Expression in Chimamanda Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus*

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Abstract

This paper identifies Chimamanda Adichie as a post-colonial African female writer who shows her African consciousness and commitment by creating characters who are awakened and grounded in their culture. Adichie in *Purple Hibiscus* explores the Igbo culture where she comes from through her characters who uphold the customs and traditions of their people. Using the post-colonial theory that rejects western values and celebrates African cultural identities and values, this paper argues that Adichie creates characters who express their culture unashamedly and undermine imperialism. The paper therefore concludes that Adichie's characters' stance represents Africa's stance against cultural exploitation since Africans still cherish their cultures, traditions, norms, values and cosmology. An aspect of style such as language use has also been deployed by the author to explicate the theme.

Key words: Culture, Expression, Post-colonialism

Le Résumé

Cet article identifie Chimamanda Adichie comme une écrivaine africaine postcoloniale qui montre sa conscience et son engagement africain en créant des personnages qui sont éveillés et enracinés dans leur culture. Dans *Purple Hibiscus*, Adichie explore la culture Igbo d'où elle vient à travers ses personnages qui défendent les coutumes et les traditions de leurs peuples. Utilisant la théorie postcoloniale qui rejette les valeurs occidentales et célèbre les identités et les valeurs culturelles africaines, cet article soutient qu'Adichie crée des personnages qui expriment leur culture sans honte et se moquent de l'impérialisme. L'article conclut donc que la position des personnages d'Adichie représente la position de l'Afrique contre l'exploitation culturelle puisque les Africains chérissent encore leurs cultures, traditions, normes, valeurs et cosmologie. Un aspect du style tel que l'utilisation de la langue a également été utilisé par l'auteur pour expliquer le thème.

Mots-clés : Culture, Expression, Post-colonialisme.

Introduction

Culture is the way of life of a people; it takes into cognizance their values, languages, beliefs, norms and tradition, customs and names which have been transmitted from one generation to another. Ini Uko in *Gender and Identity* argues that:

Culture provides a wealthy resource from which society and human beings draw explanations of issues and obtain answers to their questions. As members of the same society, people draw from culture to authenticate their activities, beliefs and matters of historicity. A dialectical relationship

emerges between society and culture as society relies on culture to elucidate issues, while culture needs society to become actualized and concrete. (1)

In the same vein, Chike Ekeopara in *Ethical Order and Stability in Traditional Igbo Society* notes that “Culture embraces all the values, norms and ethical principles which are put in place by a people to guide its patterns of social relations and interactions in order to ensure order and stability of society” (18).

Cultural expression in the context of this paper is the unequivocal display of African values and tenets by Adichie’s characters which undermines and contradicts western values and ideology.

Colonialism brought western education and religion that undermines the traditional religion of the African people. Chimamanda Adichie in *Purple Hibiscus* calls for a revolt and resistance against all forms of imperialistic ideals and system that tend to undermine the African cosmology thereby making Africans to lose faith in themselves. Adichie explores the reclamation of the African culture from the colonialists by creating characters who subvert western ideals.

Post-colonialism is a literary theory which undermines Western ideas and values that tend to oppress African values. Seldon and Widdowson in *A Reader’s Guide to Contemporary Literary Theory* argue that “Post-colonialism seeks to undermine the imperialist subject” (189). In the same vein, Chinyere Nwahunanya in *Literary Criticism, Critical Theory and Postcolonial African Literature* argues that:

The issues raised in post-colonial criticism includes the dilemmas of developing a national identity in the wake of colonial rule, the ways in which writers from colonized countries attempt to articulate and celebrate their cultural identities and reclaim them from colonizers; how knowledge of subordinate people is produced and used, and the ways in which the literature of the colonial powers is used to justify colonialism through the perpetuation of the images of the colonized as inferior. (41)

Adichie is a postcolonial African female writer who shows her African consciousness by recreating characters that are awakened and grounded in their culture. She joins other African female writers to give a voice to the female gender in particular and Africans in general. Onyemaechi Udumukwu in *Signature of Women* acknowledges Adichie’s feat when he posits that “*Purple Hibiscus* is exemplary of women because it adopts the element of voice as a veritable strategy for the constitution of African postcolonial discourse” (175). Also corroborating, Chibueze Orie in *Who is a Woman Being* argues that Adichie through *Purple Hibiscus* raises a “finger of protest pointing at unfriendliness, cruelty...to mobilize support to pull down the threatening wall of patriarchy, an ingredient of post-coloniality” (29).

Adichie in her fiction explores the Igbo culture where she comes from, which may be different from those of other ethnic groups. In recognition of the cultural diversities of each ethnic group in Africa, Catherine Acholonu in *Motherism: The Afro-Centric Alternative to Feminism* states the “African ethnic groups or cultural groups are indeed nations unto themselves each possessing its own individual cultural threats, language, identity, its own traditions and customs which set it apart from the rest” (2). Therefore, the cultural expression discussed in this paper is as it applies to Igbo culture.

Dimensions of Cultural Expression

In *Purple Hibiscus*, Auntie Ifeoma, though well-educated and trained by the missionaries like her brother, Eugene, upholds the customs and traditions of her people; that is why she still values her father, Papa-Nnukwu, who is a traditionalist. She cherishes the *Mmuo* Masquerade which Eugene abhors. Therefore, she is an embodiment of the Igbo cultural expression; that is why the narrator describes her entrance into Eugene's house thus:

Auntie Ifeoma drove into the compound just as we finished breakfast. When she barged into the dining room upstairs, I imagined a proud ancient forebear, walking miles to fetch water in homemade clay pots, nursing babies until they walked and talked, fighting wars with matchets sharpened on sun-warmed stone. She filled a room (*Purple Hibiscus*80).

Adichie creates Auntie Ifeoma in the image of the traditional Igbo women who complemented the men in their roles. Although she does not have a chieftaincy title like her brother, Eugene, she performs the socially ascribed roles to the male gender. She assumes the role of the family head, both in her nuclear family after the death of her husband, and the head of the extended family which Eugene had abandoned because his father is a traditionalist. Ifeoma takes care of their father Papa-Nnukwu and makes sure he is given good medical attention when he is sick till when he finally dies. To display his self-righteousness, after the death of their father, Eugene suggests a Christian burial for their father, but Ifeoma resists it:

Auntie Ifeoma got up and started to shout. Her voice was unsteady. "I will put my dead husband's grave for sale, Eugene, before I give our father a Catholic funeral. Do you hear me? I said I will sell Ifediora's grave first! Was our father a Catholic? I ask you, Eugene, was he a Catholic? *Uchugbagi!*" Auntie Ifeoma snapped her fingers at Papa; she was throwing a curse at him. Tears rolled down her cheeks. She made choking sounds as she turned and walked into her bedroom. (*Purple Hibiscus*186-187)

Ifeoma subverts gender role prescription by her function in the family. She respects her father Papa-Nnukwu's religious stance even in death. She shows her firm belief in the culture and religion of her people despite her Christian faith, because she sees the double standard life displayed by Eugene who professes Catholicism. In relation to this fact, Elechi Amadi in *Ethics in Nigerian Culture* argues that:

The imported religions, namely Christianity and Islam, do not have the same powerful hold on the people as the traditional religions, so their use as ethical instruments is not effective. (6)

This points to the efficacy of traditional religion, hence Papa-Nnukwu's strict adherence to its tenets despite the humiliation he suffers from his son, Eugene. Ifeoma fits perfectly in the social constructionists' view on gender roles. Social constructionists believe that an individual's behaviour whether masculine or feminine is influenced by the situation in which he or she finds herself. Kay Deaux in "Gender Roles and Stereotypes" acknowledges this when she asserts that "situations exert substantial influence in an individual's display of gendered behaviours" (196-197). This means that both the male and the female gender can swap roles depending on the situation.

Aunty Ifeoma, though a widow, shoulders the responsibilities of caring for her three children and their aged father. As a feminist, she does not bemoan her situation as a widow, but braces up to face the challenges of life in spite of being accused of killing her husband. Grace Etuk in *Violence Against Women* corroborates this as she states that:

In our rural communities, when men die, their wives, i.e. widows are made to go through certain ordeals in the name of mourning and burial rites in 'honour' of their dead husbands. Even when the women involved live in the cities, they are usually dragged down to their rural roots to face the ordeal. These rites and rituals are even made worse when a woman is suspected of having a hand in any way in the death of her husband. (41)

In Ifeoma's case, we are not told whether she went through these widowhood rites of having her hair shaved, wearing black clothes and others. But, as Etuk noted, "what a woman who loses her husband would observe as widowhood rites among Igbo people is to a recognizable extent a function of the woman's religion, level of awareness or education and to some extent, her economic status" (46-47). Due to the economic dependence of some women on their husbands, they become defenceless when their husbands die, therefore, they go through these widowhood rites firstly as a way of obeying the customs and traditions of their people, and secondly, to attract the sympathy of their husband's relatives who should help them take care of their children.

But Ifeoma does not need to go through all the rigours because she is educated and economically independent. She is also aware of Nigeria's law of inheritance as it pertains to the children of the deceased, as against the Igbo cultural law of inheritance which empowers the brothers of the deceased to inherit his property to the detriment of his children. In recognition of this fact, Joseph Charles in *Social Anthropology: Concept, Theory and Ethnography* states that the Court of Appeal

On a number of cases brought before it, rejected customary law practice as being inconsistent with natural justice, equity and good conscience. It has also ruled that children of the deceased, irrespective of sex are entitled to inheritance rights and should be granted such rights of inheritance to their late father's property and assets to the exclusion of other close or distant relatives. (358)

This Igbo cultural law of inheritance gives rise to the accusation of Aunty Ifeoma by the late husband's relatives that she has hidden the money he left behind. She tells us: "I don't have the strength for Ifediora's family right now. They eat more and more shit every year. The people in his *Umunna* said he left money somewhere and I have been hiding it" (*Purple Hibiscus*74). But Ifeoma is able to subvert this patriarchal law of inheritance which tends to subjugate the woman. She assumes the role of the family head since Eugene has rejected his role. She calls Beatrice Achike "my wife" (73) showing acceptance and affection to Beatrice whose the husband does not show her love.

This naming is reminiscent of woman-woman marriage where a woman marries a wife for her husband for the purpose of having male children if she has only daughters, or having children generally if she has none. Also, this naming of a relative's wife as your wife is an Igbo cultural practice which shows that the wife does not only belong to the husband, but to the whole family. But Eugene does not subscribe to that belief as he considers it as

“the remnants of ungodly traditions, the idea that it was the family and not the man alone that married a wife” (*Purple Hibiscus*73). But this is the cultural belief of the Igbo which Adichie through her character Ifeoma projects.

Aunty Ifeoma raises her children to have faith in the African culture and be proud of it; she teaches them African values. Amaka can cook while Kambili cannot because her father employs a cook for the family. But it is in Ifeoma’s house that Kambili realizes her humanity. Amaka tells Kambili:

I listen mostly to indigenous musicians. They’re culturally conscious, they have something real to say. Fela and Osadebe and Onyeka are my favourites. Oh, I’m sure you probably don’t know who they are, I’m sure you’re into American pop like other teenagers. She said “teenagers” as if she were not one, as if teenagers were a brand of people who, by not listening to culturally conscious music, were a step beneath her. (*Purple Hibiscus*118)

Ifeoma as an Igbo woman raises her children to perform their domestic chores independently, while Kambili and Jaja are novices, who need to be taught how to wash plates. Amaka teaches Kambili how to cook. Ifeoma expresses her cultural heritage by teaching her children to speak Igbo and allowing them to speak it freely, unlike Eugene who does not allow his children to speak Igbo in public places because he feels his children are civilized, implying that those who speak Igbo in public are not civilized. This proves that he is not proud of his heritage.

Amaka follows the footsteps of her mother in upholding the cultural heritage of her people by refusing to accept an English name during her confirmation. She values her Igbo name and rejects all the English names suggested to her as her confirmation name. She notes “when the missionaries first came, they didn’t think Igbo names were good enough. They insisted that people take English names to be baptized. Shouldn’t we be moving ahead? (266). Moving ahead to Amaka means reclaiming the useful elements of Igbo culture that the missionaries have destroyed. As a result of her rejection of an English name, she is not confirmed, but she is not bothered because the important thing is that she has maintained her Igbo (African) identity and cultural assertiveness.

And the next day, Easter Sunday, Amaka did not join the rest of the young people who wore all white and carried lit candles, with folded newspapers to trap the melting wax. They all had pieces of paper pinned to their clothes, with names written on them. Paul. Mary. James. Veronica. Some of the girls looked like brides, and I remembered my own confirmation, how Papa had said I was a bride, Christ’s bride, and I had been surprised because I thought the Church was Christ’s bride. (*Purple Hibiscus*267)

Amaka’s rejection of an English name symbolizes Africa’s rejection of foreign domination and assimilation. In world power politics, the oppressor represents the male and the oppressed the female, therefore, Amaka’s stance represents Africa’s stance against cultural exploitation since Africans still cherish their cultures, traditions, norms, values and way of life. As young as Amaka is, she is aware that African names link the Africans to their cultural heritage and ancestry that is why she reiterates the meaning of Igbo names thus: ‘Chiamaka’ says God is beautiful. ‘Chima’ says God knows best, ‘Chiebuka’ says God

is the greatest. Don't they all glorify God as much as 'Paul' and 'Peter' and 'Simon'?" (*Purple Hibiscus*266). Edmund Ilogu notes that "all Ibos, christian as well as non-christians, acknowledge this link with our patrilineal ancestors... (qtdin Amadi 7). In the same vein, Amadi argues that the rejection of foreign names by Africans "signals the beginning of attempts by learned Nigerian theologians to break free from the stranglehold of foreign religion and to acknowledge the beauty, wisdom and power of their own" (7).

The imposition of English names on Africans during Baptism or Confirmation in the church is another form of oppression, but the missionaries are unaware of the fact that African names are reflections of God in their lives. For instance, Chiamaka from which Amaka is derived means "God is beautiful" (266). Bolaji Idowu in *African Traditional Religion* affirms this thus: "the theophorus proper names that people bear all over Africa are a further evidence of how God is to Africans" (150).

Ifeoma loves her father and his traditional ways till he dies, and gives Papa-Nnukwu the type of burial that will give his spirit rest. She rejects vehemently Eugene's suggestion that their father be buried by the Catholic Church, because that will mean going against the wish of her father who died as a traditionalist. "Papa-Nnukwu really worried about having a proper funeral, Amaka said. Now I know he'll rest in peace" (*Purple Hibiscus*200). This is made possible by Ifeoma who stands her ground to give her father a befitting burial. Ifeoma therefore debunks the patriarchal belief that male children are more important than female children, because the female children will be married out, implying that it is the male children who will take care of their aged parents. Ifeoma's role debunks traditional gender role differentiation because Columbus Ogbujah and E. O Davies in "Ambivalent Sexism" have stated that: "Gender role then becomes a set of behavior patterns and attitudes which are stereotypically perceived as masculine or feminine within a cultural group; a personality characteristic expected of a person within a culture because of one's biological constitution" (20).

Eugene despises his father because he is a traditionalist, and anybody who does not follow Eugene's kind of religion is an enemy. He describes Papa-Nnukwu's religion as "Idol-worshipping" (*Purple Hibiscus*47). He despises his father to the extent that he limits his children's visit to Papa-Nnukwu and does not greet him. The Igbo are noted for their respect for elders. Eugene is an aberration of an average Igbo man who is expected to respect his elders, especially his father. Eugene's disregard for his father is misinterpreted by Papa-Nnukwu who equates the trinity of the Christian God to Eugene measuring equality with him, hence his repulsion. He states:

I remember the first one that came to Abba, the one they called Fada John. His face was red like palm oil; they say our type of sun does not shine in the white man's land. He had a helper, a man from Nimo called Jude. In the afternoon they gathered the children under the *ukwa* tree in the mission and taught them their religion. I did not join them, *kpa*, but I went sometimes to see what they were doing. One day I said to them, where is this god you worship? They said he was like *Chukwu*, that he was in the sky. I asked them, who is the person that was killed, the person that hangs on the wood outside the mission? They said he was the son, but that the son and the father are equal. It was then I knew that the white man was mad. The father

and the son are equal? *Tufia!* Do you see? That is why Eugene can disregard me, because he thinks we are equal. (*Purple Hibiscus*84)

Papa-Nnukwu who has been abandoned by his son just because he is a traditionalist, rejects all the mouth-watering offers Eugene makes him such as a house, a car, a driver, only if he throws away his *chi*. Papa-Nnukwu holds firm his cultural expression by his constant practice of his traditional religion. He achieves his quest for cultural expression by always calling on his ancestors. He considers Eugene's attitude towards him the result of his interaction with the missionaries. He attributes the equality of the trinity of Eugene's God to the reason Eugene despises him.

This paper also identifies cultural stereotypes evident in Kambili's school as the students are not allowed to sing the National Anthem until parents protest. Even in an African setting, imperialist tendencies still hold sway, but Adichie creates characters in the personality of parents of students in Kambili's school to protest against the loss of identity African (Igbo) children are likely to face if an urgent step is not taken to restore the bond that binds them together. The narrator gives an insight into the scenario thus

Singing the national anthem was relatively new at Daughters of the Immaculate Heart. It had started last year, because some parents were concerned that their children did not know the national anthem or the pledge. I watched the sisters as we sang. Only the Nigerian Reverend Sisters sang, teeth flashing against their dark skins. The white Reverend Sisters stood with arms folded, or lightly touching the glass rosary beads that dangled at their waists, carefully watching to see that every student's lips moved. (*Purple Hibiscus*48)

The above quotation shows the extent to which colonialism which brought Christianity tries to uproot the African people from their cultural and national heritage. The parents' rejection of neo-colonialism in the school is symbolic of Africa's rejection of the experience because colonialism came and destabilized the once stable traditional setting of the people. This rejection has been explored by Chinua Achebe in *Things Fall Apart* where Okonkwo resists colonialism with the last drop of his blood. Akachi Ezeigbo in *The Last of the Strong Ones* also creates traditional women who are stakeholders in their society, and together with their men, they fight against the whites (*Kosiri*) who are agents of colonialism. This shows that the fight against colonialism and oppression is championed by both the male and the female writers who use both genders as their characters.

Adichie uses her characters to re-echo the ideals Achebe initiated over 50 years ago in *Things Fall Apart*. Achebe's move has been supported by Ezeigbo in *The Last of the Strong Ones* where women and men in the community lay down their lives to fight the white man (*Kosiri*). Simon Gikandi in "African Literature and the Colonial Factor" argues that "one of the key motivations for producing an African literature was to restore the moral integrity and cultural autonomy of the African in the age of decolonization" (56). This is what Achebe and Ezeigbo have done in their works, and Adichie has taken over this fight of decolonizing Africa using her literary works.

However, the positive side of colonialism is the acquisition of western education which has equipped African writers to air their views in European languages. Gikandi affirms this as he states that "the emergence of African literatures in European languages

needs to be located within the crucial claim that colonized subjects had set out to use the instrument and grammar given to them by the colonizer to oppose foreign domination and assert their sovereignty” (57). The instruments and grammar of the colonizer to the Africans are education and civilization. This is the positive impact of colonialism. In the same vein, Grace Okereke in “Education as a Colonial Heritage...” states that:

Formal western education, a colonial heritage, has been a positive liberating force for Nigerian women. It has equipped them for self-definition by raising their consciousness to their subjugation by the male-dominated society. Through the concomitant economic independence, education has also equipped women with resources for survival in the face of the treacheries of life. (133)

Ifeoma is able to take up the challenge of caring for her abandoned father as a result of the colonial education which she receives which has empowered her economically.

Use of Language

In *Purple Hibiscus*, Adichie creates characters who express their African (Igbo) culture through language use. Through use of language, the characters uphold their African traditional values. Papa-Nnukwu, a traditionalist and an embodiment of patriarchy, upholds the tenets of the patriarchal system that tends to inferiorize women. Through his words, he dismisses Auntie Ifeoma as unimportant when compared to Eugene, despite her dedication to her father whom Eugene has abandoned. He says: “But you are a woman. You do not count” (83). Papa-Nnukwu in his quest for cultural expression uses language to denigrate the woman. His attitude towards the woman is embedded in traditional African society which prefers the male child to the female child.

Also, in an effort to bring out her Africanness, Adichie’s character code-switch from the English language to Igbo language. Such examples abound in the novel. We have few examples like “Lunch was fufu and *Onugbu* soup” (11). “*Ome mma, chineke, O me mma...*” (39). “*Kedunu?*” (55). Also through language use, Amaka expresses her Igbo culture by rejecting the numerous English names suggested for her Confirmation sacrament. She questions the veracity of foreign names.

Commending Adichie’s linguistic choices, Allwell Onukaogu and Ezechi Onyerionwu in *Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie: The Aesthetics of Commitment and Narrative* note that Adichie uses the:

thematic and stylistic dimensions; her subscription to a ‘vernacular’ style of English, which is couched in the speech patterns of local speakers, and her patronage of the elements of the African folk universe, such as the folktale, proverbs, riddles and other witty sayings, Adichie has paid allegiance to and demonstrated her pride in the tradition that has produced her. (305)

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to interrogate how Adichie showcases her Africanness through cultural expression. Ifeoma, though a Christian still upholds the traditional belief of her people through her love and devotion to her father who is a traditionalist. Papa-Nnukwu also forfeits the good things of life promised by his son Eugene because of his believe in the

tradition and culture of his ancestors. However, the expression of one's belief comes with tribulations; Papa-Nnukwu faces abandonment and neglect in his quest for cultural expression. Amaka also forfeits her confirmation sacrament in the Catholic Church because she sticks to her African name which gives her cultural identity. Language use as an aspect of style has also been used to explore the cultural expression of the characters.

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